

A SuperCollider-Based Spatial Audio Performance System with AR Interfaces

Hyunkyung Shin
Georgia Institute of Technology
hshin336@gatech.edu

Henrik von Coler
Georgia Institute of Technology
hvc@gatech.edu

ABSTRACT

The presented real-time interactive spatial audio performance system connects an Augmented Reality (AR) interface with performers. Virtual objects manipulated by performers' gestures are tracked with six degrees of freedom (6DoF) in real time, and the resulting data are transmitted to the audio engine via Open Sound Control (OSC). The system processes live audio input from musical instruments to support dynamic sound manipulation and spatial transformations. Higher-Order Ambisonics (HOA) is employed for immersive spatial audio rendering, which allows performers' gestures to directly control sound positioning, spectral characteristics, and dynamic modulation during live performances.

1. INTRODUCTION

Augmented Reality (AR) expands the possibilities of interactive performances by merging virtual and physical elements in real time. Despite advances in AR technology, controlling spatial audio in AR-based performances remains challenging due to latency issues, complex spatialization algorithms, and the need for seamless interaction between performers and digital sound environments. Real-time sound manipulation requires a system that captures movement data from performers and processes real-time audio input with minimal latency.

To address these challenges, this paper presents a spatial audio performance system built with SuperCollider. The system connects an AR interface with live performers, processes real-time audio input from musical instruments, and applies spatial transformations based on object movement and rotation. Motion tracking occurs within the AR interface, and the system transmits six degrees of freedom (6DoF) data to the audio engine via Open Sound Control (OSC). Higher-Order Ambisonics (HOA) enables three-dimensional spatial audio rendering, providing realistic sound source positioning in an immersive environment.

The system includes advanced sound design modules that apply spectral transformation, dynamic filtering, and spatial effects to enhance performers' expressive capabilities. Through the integration of real-time motion tracking, audio input processing, and spatialization techniques, the system allows performers to intuitively manipulate sound

within virtual environments. The system can be applied to AR live performances and immersive sound design.

2. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORKS

2.1 Computer-based Performance System

2.1.1 Computer Music Performance System (CMPS)

Figure 1. The components of a computer music performance system (Anderson and Kuivila, 1990).

A computer music performance system (CMPS) defines the fundamental structure of a computer-based performance system [1]. It comprises input devices, a control computer, synthesizers, and additional I/O devices, converting a performer's gestures into digital data for real-time processing and output. Input devices include general-purpose computer peripherals, MIDI keyboards and other traditional instrument-based controllers, and specially designed musical input devices. The control computer processes these inputs to generate sound control commands, such as note on/off signals and continuous timbre adjustments. Synthesizers receive control commands via the MIDI protocol, generate audio signals, and deliver them to performers and audiences.

2.1.2 Interactive Music System (IMS)

Interactive Music System (IMS) extends traditional musical interfaces by providing a 3D performance experience with a standard musical keyboard as the primary controller [2]. A multi-track looper allows for the creation of multiple sound sources, called Musical Agents, which function as loops of musical material. Real-time sound synthesis allows flexible timbre control through the physical interface.

The performer's body and the surrounding space are integral parts of the system. Sufficient physical room is required to interact with sound sources. An ambisonic

speaker array is used to implement spatial audio. This setup provides an immersive sound experience without the need for wearable devices.

The audio position of sound sources is visually represented in 3D space using MR technology. Motion tracking enables users to manipulate sound sources as physical objects and map their movements to target locations.

Musical agents can operate autonomously, dynamically modifying musical lines based on user input and interactions with other agents while maintaining the performer’s playing style. Users can control autonomy through the 3D visual interface, enabling or disabling autonomous behavior as needed.

2.2 Augmented Reality in Performance

AR enables new forms of artistic expression and audience engagement in performance. In the field of music, AR-based interactive visualization and composition systems have been developed to facilitate real-time interaction with music by manipulating virtual elements through hand tracking or marker recognition [3, 4].

In theatrical performance, AR has been utilized to enhance storytelling through real-time digital overlays and interactive stage design. Recent studies have proposed technologies that allow performers to directly control AR-based visual elements and synchronize digital and physical components [5].

Additionally, Audio Augmented Reality (AAR) technology employs spatialized soundscapes to guide audience interaction, providing an immersive and participatory performance experience [6]. As a medium that connects physical spaces with virtual environments, AR suggests the potential to reshape the structure of performance. With further advancements in AR-based interaction technologies, its applications in performance are expected to expand [7, 8].

2.3 OSC-based Audio Connection

OSC is a protocol widely utilized in music technology for real-time sound manipulation and spatial audio implementation. Particularly, OSC is effective when it transmits data between devices and enables real-time control over sound parameters [9]. Due to these characteristics, OSC plays a crucial role in interactive audio and spatial sound design.

OSC facilitates real-time interaction with sound through gesture-based control and enhances musical expressiveness in live performances [10]. Furthermore, it serves as a powerful tool for real-time sound synthesis by supporting the manipulation of synthesis parameters across multiple devices in distributed music systems [11].

In addition to sound synthesis, OSC is utilized in spatial audio applications to manage and control audio positioning [12], thereby facilitating precise sound placement [13]. Moreover, OSC supports multi-device synchronization for real-time collaborative sound manipulation [14].

3. SYSTEM DESIGN

The performance system integrates AR interfaces for real-time, gesture-based control. The system consists of input devices, audio processing modules, and an audio output

Figure 2. Overview of the AR performance system with two AR interfaces.

stage. Through this configuration, the system enables performers to control spatialization using hand gestures. Motion data from the AR interfaces is transmitted via OSC to SuperCollider, where spatial audio processing and encoding are performed. The processed signals are subsequently decoded and reproduced through loudspeakers, as represented in Figure 2.

3.1 AR Interface

Figure 3. 6DoF ARCube.

Two AR interfaces known as ARCube [15] are incorporated into the AR performance system to support a multi-performer environment. Performers interact with the AR interface by wearing a Head-Mounted Display (HMD). Performers can freely manipulate a cube and four objects color-coded in red, green, blue, and yellow using pinch and grab gestures (Figure 3). The cube transmits the 6DoF position data of each object via OSC.

Listing 1. OSC connection with AR Interface for xyz.

```
OSCdef('/quest/1/xyz',
{
  arg msg, time, addr, rcvPort;
  var x,y,z;
  var idx = msg[1]-1;

  ~quest_xyz_BUS[idx].setAt(0, msg[2]);
  ~quest_xyz_BUS[idx].setAt(1, msg[3]);
  ~quest_xyz_BUS[idx].setAt(2, msg[4]);
}, '/quest/1/xyz');
```

3.2 OSC Communication

OSC connections support dynamic control of sound parameters by mapping external positional data from two AR interfaces to internal SuperCollider buses (Listing 1).

The OSC module is responsible for receiving and processing real-time motion-tracking data from external devices. In the AR performance system, OSC connects two AR interfaces with SuperCollider. The system listens for incoming OSC messages and maps them to relevant control buses. This process provides spatial tracking, positional modulation, and movement-based sound transformations.

Specifically, 6DoF data generated through real-time object interaction is sent via OSC and assigned to corresponding buses in SuperCollider, as summarized in Table 1.

OSC Message	Data	Bus Assignment
/quest/1/aed	Azimuth, Elevation, Distance	quest_aed_BUS[idx]
/quest/1/xyz	X, Y, Z Position	quest_xyz_BUS[idx]
/quest/1/pry	Pitch, Roll, Yaw	quest_pry_BUS[idx]

Table 1. Mapping of 6DoF OSC messages to SuperCollider buses for real-time interaction.

3.3 Sound Design

The system integrates two different sets of modules for each instrument. These modules are designed to be compatible with a double bass and a modular synthesizer and support sound mapping based on the 6DoF of the AR interface.

As shown in Table 2, each set of modules assigns specific audio effects to four distinct virtual objects. Within each object, sound parameters are further modulated based on the object’s position along the x, y, and z axes inside the AR interface.

Virtual Objects	Sound Effects
RED	Pitch and Spatial Diffusion
GREEN	Feedback and Delay
BLUE	Bit-Crush and Freeze Effects
YELLOW	Grain Length and Density

Table 2. Core sound effects assigned to one set of four virtual objects, with position-based modulation inside the AR interface.

Although each set targets a different instrument, the sound processing modules share a common structure based on /SynthDef templates. Sound modules are adaptable and can be modified in their parameter settings and functional behaviors to match the specific characteristics of each instrument.

To further optimize sound processing based on the input characteristics of acoustic instruments, the system employs /SynthDef modules.

The following /SynthDef modules are examples of common sound processing units used for both instruments:

- **frequency_modulation:** Performs frequency modulation and wavefolding distortion.

- **spectral_delay:** Applies delay-based spectral diffusion.

However, detailed parameter settings differ between the double bass and the modular synthesizer. For example, both instruments utilize feedback and delay diffusion effects through the `quad_pdf` synthesizer, but the modulation is controlled differently by the `delaybus` and `feedbackbus` parameters. In `double_bass.scd`, the absence of explicit feedback constraints allows for more flexible modulation and broader diffusion effects. In contrast, `modular_synth.scd` employs stricter control over delay feedback, which results in a more constrained, time-dependent spectral diffusion behavior.

3.4 Spatial Rendering

Spatialization is implemented in SuperCollider. Ambisonics encoding is performed using the HOA class and multi-channel bus processing, and a customized function is introduced to improve the spatial rendering and immersion.

The following SynthDef modules present examples of HOA encoding and spatial diffusion:

- **hoa_mono_encoder:** Encodes sound using HOA coefficients for detailed spatial localization.
- **spatial_splitter:** Distributes a single object’s spatial data to multiple directions to enhance diffusion.

The `spatial_splitter` rotates an object’s azimuth value at ninety-degree intervals ($\pi/2$ radians) to create four directional outputs, while maintaining elevation and distance. This function enhances spatial spread within the Ambisonics system and increases immersion.

Gesture-driven spatialization modifies sound based on real-time position data from interactions in the AR environment. The system also uses gesture speed as a control parameter for dynamic sound effects. Position changes further generate distinct sonic characteristics.

As depicted in Figure 4, increased speed during the green object’s diagonal movement across two faces generates a wind-like sound. For the yellow object, positioning at the left corner generates a small breath effect, while the middle right side creates a stronger breath effect.

4. FUTURE WORKS

Future research will aim to enhance the technical performance and musical interaction of the AR performance system. Areas of exploration include the integration of new gesture sets to refine HOA spatialization. Another focus is the optimization of sound effects to better adapt to the input characteristics of various instruments. Spatial decoding capabilities within SuperCollider will be strengthened to achieve more accurate and dynamic spatial sound reproduction. Developing more flexible mappings between gesture data and sound parameters is expected to further enable performers to control sound in a more intuitive and expressive manner.

Finally, expanding the system to support collaborative manipulation of spatialized sound objects presents a promising direction for future development. Through this

Figure 4. Distinct sound effects achieved through spatialization: (a) speed-based effect, (b) location-based small breath effect, and (c) location-based strong breath effect.

functionality, performers and audiences will be able to interact directly within the AR environment.

5. CONCLUSION

A real-time interactive spatial audio performance system was developed by integrating AR interfaces, OSC-based data communication, and HOA for dynamic spatial sound rendering. The system enables performers to manipulate sound positioning, spectral characteristics, and dynamic modulation through hand gestures, resulting in an immersive and expressive performance. The modular architecture supports adaptability to various instruments and facilitates sound design with SuperCollider. Observations indicated that changes in gesture speed and object positioning influenced spatialized sound effects and enhanced real-time sonic interaction. The findings underscore the potential of AR-based spatial audio performance for enhancing live concerts and facilitating collaboration in musical environments.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] D. P. Anderson and R. Kuivila, "A system for computer music performance," *ACM Transactions on Computer Systems (TOCS)*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 56–82, 1990.
- [2] P. Lucas and S. Fasciani, "A Human-Agents Music Performance System in an Extended Reality Environment," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression (NIME)*. NIME, 2023.
- [3] G. S. R. Reddy and D. Rompapas, "Liquid Hands: Evoking Emotional States via Augmented Reality Music Visualizations," in *ACM International Conference on Interactive Media Experiences (IMX '21)*. ACM, 2021, pp. 305–310.
- [4] K. Poddar and B. Sharma, "Enhancing Music Composition with Marker-Based Augmented Reality Technology," in *2024 4th International Conference on Sustainable Expert Systems (ICSES)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 1319–1323.
- [5] D. Lisowski, K. Ponto, S. Fan, C. Probst, and B. Sprecher, "Augmented Reality into Live Theatrical Performance," in *Springer Handbook of Augmented Reality*. Springer, 2023, pp. 433–450.
- [6] A. N. Nagele, V. Bauer, P. G. T. Healey, J. D. Reiss, H. Cooke, T. Cowlshaw, C. Baume, and C. Pike, "Interactive Audio Augmented Reality in Participatory Performance," *Frontiers in Virtual Reality*, vol. 1, 2021.
- [7] L. Turchet, R. Hamilton, and A. Çamci, "Music in Extended Realities," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 15 810–15 832, 2021.
- [8] W. Li, "Musical Instrument Performance in Augmented Virtuality," in *6th International Conference on Digital Signal Processing (ICDSP)*. ACM, 2022, pp. 91–98.
- [9] M. Wright, "Open Sound Control: An Enabling Technology for Musical Networking," *Organised Sound*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 193–200, 2005.
- [10] D. Wessel and M. Wright, "Problems and Prospects for Intimate Musical Control of Computers," *Computer Music Journal*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 11–22, 2002.
- [11] Y. Masuyama, Y. Bando, K. Yatabe, Y. Sasaki, M. Onishi, and Y. Oikawa, "Self-Supervised Neural Audio-Visual Sound Source Localization via Probabilistic Spatial Modeling," in *2020 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 4848–4854.
- [12] J.-M. Jot, R. Audfray, M. Hertensteiner, and B. Schmidt, "Rendering Spatial Sound for Interoperable Experiences in the Audio Metaverse," in *2021 Immersive and 3D Audio: From Architecture to Automotive (I3DA)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–15.
- [13] M. Zbyszyński, H. Déjardin, D. Marston, and G. L. Nost, "ADM-OSC: An Industry Initiative for Communicating Object-Based Audio Data," in *2023 Immersive and 3D Audio: From Architecture to Automotive (I3DA)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [14] A. Schmeder, A. Freed, and D. Wessel, "Best Practices for Open Sound Control," in *Proceedings of the Linux Audio Conference (LAC)*. Utrecht, Netherlands: LAC, 2010.
- [15] H. Shin and H. von Coler, "ARCube: Hybrid Spatial Interaction for Immersive Audio," in *Proceedings of the ACM Symposium on Spatial User Interaction (SUI '24)*. ACM, 2024, pp. 1–3.